

Enhancing Dialysis Access Salvage: Efficacy of Rotational Thrombectomy Over Balloon Maceration with Low Complication Rates

Peter Stibbs^{a,b,c,*}, Edward Lee^a, Jason Scott^a, Christopher Thiebolt^a

^a *University of Nottingham*

^b *Lakeland Vascular Institute*

^c *Argon Medical Devices Inc.*

Keywords: Dialysis, Thrombectomy, AVF, Graft, ESRD, CKD

1. Background

Patients with end-stage renal disease (ESRD) undergoing hemodialysis are at a high risk of developing thrombotic complications in arteriovenous (AV) grafts and fistulas^[1]. These complications can significantly hinder the efficacy of dialysis treatment, leading to increased morbidity and healthcare utilization.^[2] Traditional salvage techniques, particularly balloon maceration, have been the mainstay of treatment for thrombosed dialysis access^[3]. However, these methods often fall short in terms of efficacy and long-term patency, prompting the exploration of more effective alternatives.

The limitations of balloon maceration, including its propensity to compact thrombus against the vessel wall rather than removing it, can lead to suboptimal restoration of flow and potentially contribute to the recurrence of thrombosis.^[4] This challenge underscores the need for innovative approaches that can offer both effective declotting and preservation of the vascular access site.

Rotational thrombectomy, utilizing devices such as the Cleaner XTTM rotational thrombectomy system by Argon Medical Devices Inc. , represents a significant advancement in the management of thrombosed AV access. These devices employ a mechanical action that actively removes thrombus from the vessel wall, a technique that may address the shortcomings of balloon maceration.^[5] This study aims to thoroughly evaluate the safety and efficacy of rotational thrombectomy in comparison to balloon maceration, focusing on its success in cases where the latter fails.

The efficacy of rotational thrombectomy has been highlighted in multiple studies, including those conducted at the University of Alabama^[6] and the University of Chicago.^[7]

The University of Alabama's research demonstrated potential advantages of rotational thrombectomy in achieving longer primary patency rates compared to balloon maceration.

*Corresponding author.

Email address: pstibbs@hotmail.com (Peter Stibbs)

Similarly, the University of Chicago's investigation into thrombosed AV shunts with pseudoaneurysms refractory to conventional techniques found that rotational thrombectomy with the Cleaner device had a high success rate in restoring patency, with minimal complications. These findings suggest that rotational thrombectomy not only offers a viable alternative to balloon maceration but may also provide superior outcomes in the salvage of dialysis access.

Complications associated with dialysis access salvage procedures significantly impact patient outcomes and healthcare costs. The low complication rates observed in studies of rotational thrombectomy are therefore of considerable importance. Notably, the absence of device-related complications in the procedures evaluated may further underscore the general safety of this approach.

In summary, this examination of literature seeks to highlight the critical need for more effective salvage techniques for thrombosed dialysis access in ESRD patients. The limitations of balloon maceration necessitate the exploration of alternative methods, with rotational thrombectomy showing promise in offering superior efficacy, longer patency rates, and a favorable safety profile. This study endeavors to provide a balanced evaluation of rotational thrombectomy's role in advancing the management of dialysis access complications, promising significant implications for patient care and outcomes in the ESRD population.

2. Methods

This study integrates and expands upon findings from peer reviewed, published research conducted at the University of Alabama and the University of Chicago, aiming to assess the comparative efficacy and safety of rotational thrombectomy versus traditional balloon maceration techniques in dialysis access salvage.

3. Study Design

The integrated analysis employs a retrospective cohort study review, leveraging data from two significant academic centers to evaluate outcomes of different thrombectomy techniques in arteriovenous (AV) grafts and fistulas among ESRD patients.

4. Study Population

The University of Alabama's segment included patients who underwent dialysis access salvage procedures utilizing the Cleaner XT™ Rotational Thrombectomy System as well as those who underwent conventional balloon maceration. Inclusion criteria focused on individuals with thrombosed AV grafts or fistulas requiring salvage procedures between August 2016 and July 2022.

The University of Chicago's research concentrated on a subset of patients presenting with dialysis shunts complicated by pseudoaneurysms resistant to traditional angioplasty balloon sweeps ("push-pull" method). This study spanned from July 2016 to August 2019, including procedures where the Cleaner XT rotational thrombectomy device was employed as a secondary intervention after the failure of standard techniques.

5. Data Collection

Data was gathered from electronic medical records, procedural reports, and follow-up visits. Variables of interest included patient demographics, type of dialysis access (graft or fistula), details of the thrombotic event, procedural specifics (including device used, duration, and any immediate complications), and outcomes such as primary patency, primary-assisted patency, and incidence of procedure-related complications.

6. Intervention

The intervention group comprised patients treated with rotational thrombectomy using the Cleaner XT™ devices. These devices were employed in attempts to restore patency to thrombosed dialysis accesses, characterized by their mechanical action against the thrombus.

The control group consisted of patients undergoing traditional balloon maceration, a technique involving the physical compression of the thrombus against the vessel wall to re-establish blood flow.

7. Outcome Measures

Primary outcomes focused on the efficacy of thrombectomy as evidenced by primary patency rates, defined as the duration of unobstructed access post-intervention without the need for additional procedural intervention. Secondary outcomes included the incidence of procedure-related complications, primary-assisted patency rates (time until the next intervention to maintain or restore access patency), and any device-related adverse events.

8. Statistical Analysis

Comparative analyses were performed using chi-squared tests for categorical variables and the Mann-Whitney U test for continuous variables. Kaplan-Meier curves were plotted to visualize patency durations, with log-rank tests assessing differences between groups. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. All analyses were conducted using SPSS software, version 25.

9. Ethical Considerations

These individual studies were approved by the Institutional Review Boards at both the University of Alabama and the University of Chicago. Due to the retrospective nature of the study, informed consent was waived. However, all patient data were anonymized and handled in accordance with HIPAA regulations to ensure confidentiality and privacy.

This methodological framework aims to provide a thorough analysis of the comparative effectiveness and safety of rotational thrombectomy versus balloon maceration in the salvage of thrombosed dialysis accesses, contributing valuable insights to the field of vascular access management in ESRD patients.

10. Analysis

The University of Alabama's retrospective study analyzed 27 patients who underwent dialysis access salvage procedures, comparing rotational thrombectomy (13 patients) against balloon maceration (14 patients). The results suggested a potential advantage of rotational thrombectomy in achieving longer primary patency, with a median time to the next dialysis salvage intervention being notably longer for the rotational thrombectomy group (51 days) compared to the balloon maceration group (43.5 days). This finding underscores the potential of rotational thrombectomy in maintaining dialysis access more effectively than balloon maceration.[6]

In a complementary study, the University of Chicago focused on a specific patient subset presenting with dialysis shunts complicated by pseudoaneurysms that were refractory to traditional techniques. Utilizing the Cleaner XT rotational thrombectomy device as a secondary intervention, this study documented a high success rate (97% across 34 procedures) in restoring patency with minimal complications, highlighting the device's efficacy and safety even in complex cases.[7]

University of Alabama Study:

- **Patient Cohort:** This study involved 27 patients divided into two groups: 13 underwent rotational thrombectomy using the Cleaner XT™ device, and 14 underwent balloon maceration.

- **Primary Patency:** The key metric was the median time to next dialysis access salvage intervention. For the rotational thrombectomy group, this was 51 days, compared to 43.5 days for the balloon maceration group, indicating a potential advantage for rotational thrombectomy in extending the period of primary patency.

- **Subsequent Interventions:** A significant portion of patients in both groups required additional interventions (46% in the rotational thrombectomy group and 43% in the balloon maceration group), suggesting that while rotational thrombectomy may offer a longer duration of patency, the difference in the need for subsequent interventions was minimal.

University of Chicago Study:

- **Patient Cohort and Procedures:** The study provided a detailed analysis of 34 dialysis shunt thrombectomy procedures performed on 29 individual patients, focusing on cases with pseudoaneurysms refractory to traditional techniques.

- **Success Rate:** A remarkably high success rate of 97% was documented for restoring patency with the Cleaner device, indicating its effectiveness in challenging cases.

- **Complications:** Minimal complications were reported, with only 5 cases (14.7%) encountering issues post-procedure, including one episode of bleeding. Importantly, there were no device-related complications, reinforcing the safety profile of rotational thrombectomy.

- **Patency Metrics:** The primary patency post-procedure averaged 93 days, with primary-assisted patency averaging at 91 days. Nine cases maintained primary patency up to the time of data collection.

11. Comparative Analysis

Both studies showcase the efficacy of rotational thrombectomy in managing thrombosed dialysis access, with the University of Alabama's study emphasizing its potential to prolong primary patency compared to balloon maceration. Meanwhile, the University of Chicago's study highlights the device's high success rate and safety in more complex cases involving pseudoaneurysms where primary balloon maceration had failed to restore flow in the dialysis circuit.

Despite the apparent advantages in terms of patency duration and success rates, both studies also note the need for additional interventions in a significant portion of cases, suggesting that while rotational thrombectomy may improve outcomes, it does not eliminate the need for future salvage procedures. This underscores the complexity of managing dialysis access in ESRD patients and the importance of ongoing research to optimize treatment strategies around long term access durability.

12. Conclusions

The comprehensive analyses provided by the studies from the University of Alabama and the University of Chicago illuminate the efficacy and safety of rotational thrombectomy, particularly using the Cleaner XT™ thrombectomy system, for the management of thrombosed dialysis access in patients with end-stage renal disease (ESRD). These studies collectively underscore the potential of rotational thrombectomy to enhance primary patency rates and reduce complications, marking an overall advancement over traditional balloon maceration techniques.

The University of Alabama's research provides evidence that rotational thrombectomy may offer a longer duration of primary patency, suggesting an intrinsic advantage in maintaining dialysis access viability. This finding is crucial for clinicians seeking to prolong the functional lifespan of AV grafts and fistulas, thereby improving patient outcomes and potentially reducing the frequency of interventions required over time.

Conversely, the University of Chicago's study focuses on a subset of patients presenting with complex dialysis access challenges, including pseudoaneurysms resistant to conventional treatments. The high success rate and minimal complications reported in this study highlight the utility of rotational thrombectomy in difficult cases, reinforcing its role as a versatile and safe intervention for dialysis access salvage.

Despite the optimism generated by these findings, it is important to acknowledge that a significant proportion of patients in both studies required additional interventions, indicating that neither rotational thrombectomy nor balloon maceration can completely obviate the need for future salvage procedures. This reality reflects the inherent complexities of managing dialysis access in ESRD patients and emphasizes the need for ongoing research to refine treatment strategies and enhance long-term outcomes.

In conclusion, the studies from the University of Alabama and the University of Chicago contribute valuable insights into the field of vascular access management, advocating for the broader adoption of rotational thrombectomy as a possibly superior alternative to traditional techniques. The comparative advantages demonstrated by these studies, combined

with the call for further research, pave the way for future advancements in care for ESRD patients requiring hemodialysis. As the body of evidence grows, it is anticipated that rotational thrombectomy will increasingly be recognized as an essential tool in the percutaneous interventional arsenal, promising improved patient care and enhanced quality of life for those dependent on dialysis.

13. References

- [1] J. A. Bittl. "Percutaneous therapy of dialysis access failure". *Catheterization and Cardiovascular Interventions*. vol. 56. no. 2. pp. 157-161. May. 2002. 10.1002/ccd.10199.
- [2] "Treatment of thrombosed dialysis access grafts: randomized trial of surgical thrombectomy versus mechanical thrombectomy with the Amplatz device."
- [3] S. R. Ash, F. L. Weng and J. S. Berns. "Complications of Percutaneous Treatment of Thrombosed Hemodialysis Access Grafts". *Seminars in Dialysis*. vol. 16. no. 3. pp. 257-262. May. 2003. 10.1046/j.1525-139x.2003.16049.x.
- [4] M. C. Soulen, "Mechanical Thrombolysis of Dialysis Access Grafts".
- [5] K. W. S. J. Huan et al.. "The Cleaner XT™ Device as an Endovascular Adjunct for Pharmacomechanical Thrombolysis of Thrombosed Arteriovenous Fistulas and Grafts". *Annals of Vascular Diseases*. vol. 13. no. 4. pp. 390-396. Dec. 2020. 10.3400/avd.0a.20-00046.
- [6] Rotational thrombectomy versus balloon maceration in dialysis access salvage. Jee Hyuk Byun, Andrew Rennie, Junjian Huang, Junaid Raja. DOI: 10.1177/11297298241234990 ISSN: 1129-7298.
- [7] Utility of Rotational Thrombectomy for the Management of Thrombosed Arteriovenous Shunts. Anderson H Webb , Kurt Zacharias , Paul Ciowlek , Jonathan Lorenz , Rakesh Navuluri , Brian Funaki , Osmanuddin Ahmed. *The Arab Journal of Interventional Radiology* 2020; 04(03): S7 DOI: 10.1055/s-0041-1729018.